

THE MODERNIZED PARTS CONTROL AUTOMATED SUPPORT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT: This paper will provide an understanding of a new Automated Data Processing (ADP) system - the Modernized Parts Control Automated Support System (MPCASS) and how it assists to accomplish the DoD Parts Control Program. MPCASS is an on-line system which automates many manual processes, operates in near real time, and can virtually become paperless. MPCASS can be used to access many files for information. This paper includes background, system description and operation, benefits, status, operational experience, and conclusion.

INTRODUCTION: The Defense Electronics Supply Center (DESC) function is to support Defense Logistics Agency's (DLA) mission of providing effective logistics support, contract administration, and technical service; therefore, DESC established inventory management for over 980,000 stock numbers and obligates over 700,000 dollars daily in support of 2,400 purchase requisitions. Other mission activities include: component engineering and Engineering Standardization, preparation of military specifications, administration of the Qualification Program, and management of the DoD Parts Control Program. In the early 70s,

DESC was charged to study the systems acquisition process and devise a program to use the expertise of a central group of part specialists to slow down the proliferation of piece parts entering the logistic support system. The DoD Military Parts Control Advisory Group (MPCAG) was chartered in 1972 by order of the Office of the Assistant Secretary of Defense (Installation and Logistics) to put various engineering practices into operation.

Subsequently, the DoD Parts Control Program became a mandated requirement for system acquisition by the Secretary of Defense in 1983 and MPCAGs now exist at the DLA centers in Dayton and Columbus, OH, Philadelphia, PA, and Richmond, VA. This paper will discuss the evolution of the tool used by the MPCAGs to meet the challenge of responding to technical evaluations for about 80,000 submittals per year in direct support some 900 contracts which have been let by DoD and other Federal or Civil agencies.

BACKGROUND: The DoD Parts Control Program promotes the use of the standard military parts during the design and development, production, and modification of equipments and weapon systems. Program

operation is covered by DoD Instruction 5000.2 and the program implementation is achieved by specific contract reference to MIL-STD-965 (see figure 1). MPCAGs support the program by providing an engineering review of parts submissions by contractors and replacing nonpreferred parts with preferred standard military parts. Also shown in Figure 1 are the contract requirements and procedures.

CONTRACT REQUIREMENT

Figure 1. Parts Control Program Contract Requirements Pre and Post MPCASS

The early tool for the support of the program was the Parts Control Automated Support System (PCASS). PCASS was operated in a batch mode with a large volume of paper being processed through many manual steps. Because of the amount of effort to support the many hundreds of contracts, the PCASS tool became inadequate; therefore, MPCASS development began in the 1983 timeframe. Figure 2 shows the PCASS procedure. The immediate benefit from MPCASS (the elimination of manual paper handling process and multiple inputs for each evaluation received) is shown in figure 3.

PART APPROVAL REQUEST EVALUATION FLOW PRIOR TO MPCASS

Figure 2. Part Evaluation Flow Prior to MPCASS

PART APPROVAL REQUEST

Figure 3. MPCASS Part Approval Request Data Flow

MPCASS will be listed as the preferred method of operation in the recently revised issue of MIL-STD-965B.

The operation of parts control has resulted in the creation of a database which consists of over one million control numbers with over two million part numbers being presented. Data is archived off of the system after five years. Active contracts are exempt from this process.

PROCEDURE AND DOCUMENTATION CHANGE: The immediate change with MPCASS is the elimination of paper when operating in the electronic environ-

ment. MPCASS provides both the System Program Office (SPO) and contractor with the capability to determine the status of a parts submission upon completion of the evaluation process by the MPCAG. The immediate benefit of this capability to the decision process is evident; even if the only consideration is mail time. With the intent of MPCASS being to remove the paper from the process, an electronic audit trail to verify contractor submissions and evaluation receipts is being developed. Completion of this audit trail will lead to contractual requirements which will reflect a total electronic environment.

ADP PROCESSING UNDER MPCASS:

The MPCASS architecture is comprised of three distinct levels: a system mainframe, an intermediate minicomputer, and personal computers as workstations. External users interface with MPCASS via the DLA network, which provides a worldwide network capability with 6 regional nodal sites situated across the United States. Nodal use provides for reduced operational costs along with system security. Reduced cost is provided by proximity of the nodes to contractor facilities; while security is assured by way of a dial-back procedure with additional controls at each MPCAG. (Note: The dial-back call cost is currently borne by the government, but may be passed on to the user in the future.) System access is requested by external users by contacting the nearest MPCAG. The basic information required to obtain access is: requestor identity including last six digits of the social security number, organization

affiliation, equipment type, communication software, and phone number for dial-back authentication. The contract code for file access to the MPCAGs is also required.

MPCASS presents a menu driven system and provides input screens which employ on-line edits, help screens, and tutorials. Data is routed automatically to the proper MPCAG based upon the federal supply class of the submitted part. Inputs are grouped into a uniquely identified package and then tracked by an automated procedure which provides package and item status to the MPCAG contract manager, contractor, and SPO. Specific contract data is protected by cross checks of the logon process to contract code. Evaluation is provided for each submission based on cross-reference, history, and quality checking files, such as an internal problem part file, the Government/Industry Data Exchange Program (GIDEP), and the Diminishing Manufacturing Source (DMS) case file. Internally, the entire evaluation processing occurs on-line with several levels of review and approval prior to release of the evaluation for access by external users. All workload is automatically routed to the proper engineer and the evaluation records are added to the proper package record. A workload tracking system is provided for all users.

SYSTEM STRUCTURE, SIZE, AND

LANGUAGE: The MPCASS shown in figure 4 uses a three-tier architecture consisting of an IBM 370 mainframe equivalent, a Gould 9050 minicomputer, and Zenith 248s serving as workstations for engineers and managers.

Figure 4. MPCASS System Architecture

The programming on the Gould 9050 is in C language; while the mainframe language used is COBOL using derivations from DLA systems operational programs. There are over 190 files used in MPCASS at the mainframe level and over 64 database files and numerous sequential files used at the minicomputer level. Data is updated through a combination of multi-daily cycles and on-line inputs. There are 65 host processes available to the external user and 66 on-line processes available to the internal MPCAG user.

USER APPLICATIONS: Figure 5 shows a typical menu shown to the user upon system access.

- (A) BASIC PACKAGE CONTROL FILE INQUIRY
- (B) BASIC PACKAGE XREF FILE INQUIRY
- (C) CONTRACT DATA MASTER FILE INQUIRY
- (D) DMS FILE INQUIRY
- (E) DOCUMENT/PART NUMBER INQUIRY
- (F) ENGINEERING ITEM CODE INQUIRY
- (G) GIDEP FILE INQUIRY
- (H) INACTIVE FOR NEW DESIGN FILE INQUIRY
- (I) PART NUMBER XREF FILE INQUIRY
- (J) PARTS CONTROL MASTER FILE INQUIRY
- (K) DISPLAY INPUT AND TUTORIAL MENU

Figure 5. Mainframe Contractor Menu

Some areas of interest in figure 5 are:

BASIC PACKAGE CONTROL and XREF FILE INQUIRIES. These files provide the user with status of input part packages and indicate the status of each evaluation.

CONTRACT DATA MASTER FILE INQUIRY. This file provides particular information for a contract including contact points, transaction history, and part level requirements.

DMS/GIDEP FILE INQUIRIES. These files provide cross-reference data between part numbers and DMS case numbers and GIDEP Alert numbers.

INACTIVE FOR DESIGN FILE INQUIRY. This file provides a list of part numbers which are classified as "inactive for design" by the MPCAGs.

DISPLAY INPUT AND TUTORIAL MENU. This selection moves the user to the inputs and tutorials menu which provides details of the functional system process.

While this discussion of menus is not all inclusive, it does provide an indication of the scope and capability of MPCASS. The development and design of MPCASS were achieved through the joint efforts of the DLA Systems Automation Center, Columbus, OH, and DESC with direction from DLA. Development and design presented a challenge because direction required the use of inventory hardware systems as the application platform.

BENEFITS OF MPCASS: MPCASS produces a much simplified process by eliminating the completion of forms and the mailings to/between/from the MPCAGs. At its worst, DESC was averaging nearly 20 days to respond to parts control submittals under PCASS. Now,

submittals are responded to in an average of 9 to 10 days with over 85% of responses being completed in 15 days or less. Some MPCASS options will give immediate results. Since many on-line databases are available and various checks and balances are built into the system, evaluation quality being provided has improved significantly. The system design is such that it will support both large and small users; i.e., input from paper and output response of paper can still occur. With the built-in electronic mail system (known as I-Mail), it is possible to electronically "correspond" with any of the registered system users. In addition, MPCASS is available to users around-the-clock. Direct access allows the user to assess and manage the parts control effort for the program development. MPCASS begins the establishment of a trend and direction in technology and encourages the user to progress toward ADP.

UNIVERSAL APPLICATION: The MPCASS design is universal in nature and can be applied and used by all military services and their contractors. The DoD Parts Control Program and MPCASS can be applied through common contract requirements, Statements of Work, and Data Items. MPCASS provides the opportunity to establish a much better relationship and knowledge among the SPOs, contractors, and MPCAGs. The system design provides the single point of entry concept in order to input initial parts control requests for any of the four MPCAGs.

EFFECTIVITY/PRODUCTIVITY: The on-line help/tutorials, part approval request input,

Government Furnished Baseline selection input, mail system, workload tracking and status, master file inquiries, and interface lead to improvement in functionality for the contractor and SPO. Internal improvements have also been achieved because of master file ad hoc query, automated workload routing and multiple approval levels, automated routing of workload among the MPCAGs, on-line maintenance of master files, automated Defense Logistics Services Center interface, and the use of system generated letters. All of these features have provided for improvement in response time, decrease in resource needs, and better management, visibility, and control of the parts control activities. Under MPCASS, the user no longer has the need to wait for overnight processing or to deal solely with paper being passed from desk-to-desk.

OPERATIONAL EXPERIENCE:

MPCASS has been in operation for nearly two years and has been shown to be an effective operational system which will continue to improve as more enhancements are programmed. In FY91 at DESC, over 67,000 technical evaluations were processed using MPCASS. Both external and internal users exercised the many features of MPCASS in processing their workload to achieve overall improvements. The SPO at the U. S. Army Missile Command, Huntsville, AL, has indicated the operating environment of MPCASS has reduced response time to contractors from six weeks to two weeks. Numerous contractors have also shown significant improvements in parts control accomplishments attributable directly to

MPCASS. Indications are that MPCASS will become a tool the Defense Contract Management Command can employ to monitor the contractor's compliance with contracted parts control requirements.

STATUS OF MPCASS: DESC began active operation of MPCASS in Jun 90 with the transfer of data from the old PCASS. In FY91, we supported 1,037 systems contracts with an improved response time from previous PCASS operational years and the quality level of technical evaluations also improved. At present, MPCASS supports over 150 external users of the system, while providing internal support to over 300 managers, engineers, and technicians at the four MPCAGs. As new contracts are let, the number of external users will continue to grow. MPCASS is modular in design, with parts control being the linchpin of the total system. Management of standardization projects (for which DESC acts as agent or assignee) occurs under the Specifications and Standards Module. When the Qualification Module becomes available, it will provide for the administration of the Qualification program (part suppliers verifying they meet the military specification requirements are placed on a Qualified Products List or Qualified Manufacturers List) and listing information to the users. When programmed, the Test Lab Module will provide on-line test lab data to the evaluator during the part evaluations. The design of the Qualification and Test Lab Modules will be completed during the next phase of the project. Completion will be dependent upon the resource allocations to the project.

PLANNED ENHANCEMENTS: The original MPCASS management requirements recognized the need to have documentation digitized in an electronic format in order to complete the transition of the process to an electronic environment. The MPCASS design team is now defining the requirements for this capability. Additional areas which are under active development at this time are: establishment of a system audit trail to provide for elimination of correspondence from the process; enhanced remote operations to provide for active interface by parts control personnel at remote sites; provide bulk up-load and down-load capability; and provide for the application of MPCASS in the operational logistics arenas, such as pre-provisioning screening, supply support requests, and item entry control. The plan is to take advantage of the efforts expended in the parts control engineering decision process and apply it to other logistics disciplines. The objective is to simply move MPCASS into a near paperless environment.

CONCLUSION: MPCASS has been a successful tool in support of the Parts Control Program. In this era of down-sizing of DoD operations, MPCASS can provide the promise of cost reductions in support of DoD system acquisitions. MPCASS was developed with minimal cost for advanced technology equipment and software. The parts control process and the MPCASS tool are in a unique and arrantly crucial position within the DoD environment. This position provides for the use and application of MPCASS in the many aspects and disciplines associated

with the Standardization,
Acquisition, and Data arenas.

*MPCASS provides a tool today
for an efficient tomorrow.*

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